

UDC 027.7:362.4(594)

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An Evaluation**

Objective. This research aims to identify the accessibility of UIN Sunan Kalijaga Library for users with disabilities to uncover the gap between the standard of library services for people with disabilities and the condition of the library to support an accessible environment. **Methods.** This research applies qualitative methods to explore the accessibility of library services for users with disabilities using the IFLA checklist, a standard for providing library services for people with disabilities consisting of 3 main areas; physical access, media format, and service and communication. **Results.** UIN Sunan Kalijaga Library has met the most of criteria for providing services for users with disabilities. Physical access covering the area outside the library, entry to the library and access to library collections and services, is largely in accordance with the standard. However, the absence of an elevator prevents users with wheelchairs from accessing to upper floor in which the library collections are stored which means that access to library collections is hindered. To address this problem, the library provides the *Difable Corner*, a department for users of all types of disabilities. The research also found that for library collections, the library provides more for the blind, while for the deaf it is still not maximized. Therefore, the library, in collaboration with the Center for Disabilities Service provides volunteers to students for whom inclusion requirements have not yet been met. **Conclusion.** Being under the parent institution that promotes inclusive value requires UIN Sunan Kalijaga Library to provide an inclusive environment that welcomes all users regardless of their abilities. The library has made some effort to fulfill the standards for providing a library for the disabled. The gap between ideal standards and real conditions in the library related to accessibility for the disabled can be taken into consideration to improve inclusive-based library services.

Keywords: library service; people with disabilities; academic library

Introduction

The number of people with significant disabilities in this world is increasing. Based on the data from WHO, we may say that it reaches 1.3 billion persons or 16 % of the total amount of world citizens (World Health Organization, 2023). In the meantime, to speak locally of Indonesia, the number of people with significant disabilities cannot be considered small. According to the statistical data from the Center Board of Statistics, in 2022, it reached 933.893 persons, consisting of persons with various disabilities, like physical disability, sensory disability, intellectual disability, and mental disorders (Badan Pusat Statistik, n.d.). Generally speaking, people with disabilities are a group of people in a community who can only perform their daily, functional activities with difficulties. In many cases, they are even prone to health and social problems, things that normal persons do not usually risk. Some studies show that people with disabilities tend to

live low-quality lives (Vankova & Mancheva, 2015). The global trend even shows that people with disabilities are prone to exclusion both in taking benefit from community development and in taking part in it (Syifa & Hadi, 2023). This is, for whatever reason, against human rights. As said in the Constitution Number 8 Year 2016, people with disabilities are protected to live under the same law and human rights as other Indonesian citizens. This means that they receive the same right to live and access the available public facilities as other citizens do. As shown by the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (Voituriez, Morita, Giordano, Bakkour, & Shimizu, 2017) and the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (Hendriks, 2007), people with disabilities should also have the same access to education.

Nowadays people are becoming more aware of human rights and the issue of accessibility for people with disabilities gets the world's attention, manifested as it is in the regulations by International Institutions and Government Institutions, like the Americans with Disabilities Act (ADA) issued by the US Department of Justice in 1990 (Kazuye Kimura, 2018). This accessibility is so fundamental for the life quality, well-being, and engagement of individuals with disabilities in the social, economic, cultural, and political aspects of society (City of Edmonton. n.d.) that the availability of it may improve the lives of people with disabilities. A library, in this case, is a public institution that serves all kinds of users, including users with disability. In this digital era, a library needs even more to provide its users, including its disabled users, with accessibility. Actually, this library service to disabled users is not something new. Such services have long been made or performed by libraries (Ezell, Pionke, & Gunnoe, 2022; Kulikauskienė & Liukinevičienė, 2020), even before the rise of inclusive issues and regulations related to the rights of people with disabilities. They have performed library services by referring to the IFLA/UNESCO Public Library Manifesto (1994), which says that library services are given to society on the basis of equality of access for all. In the following years, this accessibility for disabled users is even stated more clearly in a service standard for disabled users developed by IFLA (Irvall & Nielsen, 2005). The standard was developed by IFLA Standing Committee of Libraries Serving Disadvantaged Persons (LSDP) and designed for all types of libraries (public, school, special, and academic libraries) aiming at: 1) assessing the existing levels of accessibility to buildings, services, materials, and programs and 2) enhancing accessibility where needed. This contains a checklist that includes three main areas; physical access, media format (special media for), and service and communication.

In addition, the principles of equity, diversity, inclusion, and accessibility (EDIA) are the core values of librarianship (Ashiq, Ur Rehman, & Warraich, 2023). In America, these core values are developed through ALA Council, in which Key Action Areas are used as guiding principles, and two of these guiding principles are related to accessibility for people with disabilities, they are Diversity and Equitable Access to Information and Library Services (American Library Association, n.d.). Librarianship is a sort of profession that uses inclusive principles in serving the user society. It concerns library services and collections that reflect various perspectives and social groups, including marginalized social groups, and a group of people with disabilities is one of them (Jaeger, Bertot, & Franklin, 2010). Furthermore, diversity and inclusion become important issues in higher education (Abu Qaadon, Hamad, & Fakhouri, 2024), as the number of students with disabilities entering universities increased in various countries such as Ireland (Ryder, n.d.) and the United States (Akinc, 2009). The increase in the number of people with disabilities attending higher education means that the number of academic library users with disabilities also increases, which requires libraries to provide library services equally for all users (Ekwelem, 2013). Some specific services for ensuring equal access are suggested by ALA such as home delivery service, remote access to the OPAC, remote electronic access to library resources, volunteer readers in the library, volunteer technology assistants in the library, American Sign

Language (ASL) interpreter or real-time captioning at library programs, and radio reading services (Clark Hunt, Cromwell, & Creel, 2024). In addition, Pionke (2017) stated the need to give priority to the space design that is accessible for all. This means that it is important to provide spaces and services that are accessible to all users. Academic libraries, primarily that have students with disabilities have to provide information services accessible to people with disabilities in a library building designed to be accessible to them.

It is necessary, then, for the Library of Sunan Kalijaga State Islamic University, under its inclusive campus parent institution, to provide services accessible to students with disabilities. As we know, students with disabilities have the same rights as other non-disabled students to access library services and collections. Based on the data from the Center for Disability Service, State Islamic University (UIN) Sunan Kalijaga has 96 students with disabilities. Therefore, it is important to study the library accessibility in this university, to see whether or not the library of this university fulfills the standards to be a library accessible for students with disabilities. This research aims to evaluate the services of the Library of Sunan Kalijaga State Islamic University by using the checklist developed by IFLA to identify possible gaps and to see with this checklist some possible below-standard aspects of the library.

Methods

A qualitative approach is used in this research. Qualitative research aims to gain a comprehensive understanding of social phenomena in their natural environments (Ugwu & Eze, 2023) and this research aims to understand comprehensively the accessibility of the UIN Sunan Kalijaga Library for users with disabilities. The research compared the IFLA Checklist and the condition of UIN Sunan Kalijaga Library concerning the accessibility for users with disabilities. Therefore, the IFLA Checklist was used as the tool to collect data. The checklist consists of three main areas: Physical access, media format, service and communication. The first area has 3 elements (Irvall & Nielsen, 2005):

1) Outside the library that includes sufficient parking spaces marked with the international symbol for the disabled, parking close to the library entrance, clear and easy-to-read signposting, unobstructed and well-lighted access paths to the entrance, the smooth and non-slip surface at the entrance, if needed, a non-slip and not too steep ramp with railings next to the stairs, railings at both sides of the ramp, entry phone accessible for deaf users.

2) Getting into the library that includes sufficient space in front of the door to allow a wheelchair to turn around, an entrance door wide enough to allow a wheelchair to enter, an automatic door opener reachable by a person in a wheelchair, no doorsteps for easy wheelchair access, glass doors marked to warn visually impaired persons, security checkpoints possible to pass through with a wheelchair/walker or other mobility aides, stairs and steps marked with a contrasting color, pictogram signs leading to elevators, well-lighted elevators with buttons and signs in Braille and synthetic speech, elevator buttons reachable from a wheelchair.

3) Access to materials and services that include the physical space, toilets, circulation desk, and reference/information desk, children's department, Department for persons with reading, hearing, and other disabilities.

The second area consists of two elements, special media formats for persons with disabilities and computers that the library must provide. The service and communication include how to train staff, special services to disabled patrons (for visually impaired persons, deaf or hearing-impaired persons, persons with reading difficulties, persons with physical disabilities, cognitively disabled persons and websites), how to provide information to disabled patrons and how to cooperate with disability organization and individuals.

Table 1

IFLA Standard Evaluating Checklist

Number	Area	Elements
1	Physical Access	1. Outside the library
		2. Getting into the library
		3. Access to materials and services
2	Media Formats	1. Special media formats for persons with disabilities
		2. Computers
3	Service And Communication	1. How to train staff
		2. Special services to patrons with disabilities
		3. How to provide information to patrons with disabilities
		4. How do you make information easy to understand?
		5. Website
		6. How to cooperate with disability organizations and individuals

Source: IFLA, Access to libraries for persons with disabilities – Checklist (2006)

Data collection and analysis

In this research, there are two data collection techniques used, observation and interview. Observation is done by observing areas related to library accessibility, like the library building and its surroundings, the service facilities, and the library collections for users with disabilities. For observation, IFLA checklist was employed to gather data by comparing the checklist and the condition of the library to identify the gap that may occur. Meanwhile, the interview with the librarians was also done to complete the data relating to policy and managerial aspects of library services for users with disabilities. The data obtained from observations and interviews were then analyzed using the steps explained by J. W. Creswell and J. D. Creswell (2018), namely organizing, reading, coding, generating a description, and finally representing the description. Organizing is carried out during the data collection. Reading the data, in this research is done by checking the entire data obtained to ensure the completeness of the data in accordance with the IFLA checklist. The next step is coding which in this research is carried out by providing a code in a table with a “v” sign to indicate conformity with the checklist and an “x” sign to indicate non-conformity with the checklist. The result of the coding will generate a general description of the accessibility of the UIN Sunan Kalijaga library based on IFLA checklist. The last step is representing the description in the qualitative narrative by exposing the gap found in this research that will be used as a basis for recommending the library to increase the accessibility of the library for users with disabilities.

Result and Discussion

The number of students with disabilities at Sunan Kalijaga State Islamic University is increasing. Based on the data from the Center for Disabilities Service, they number 95 persons

(Academic Year 2018-2023), with various kinds of disabilities, like blind, deaf, slow learner, down syndrome, autism, mental disorder, and mentally disabled. The following Table shows the details.

Table 2

Data of Students with Disabilities at Sunan Kalijaga State Islamic University

Number	Sort of disability	Amount
1	Blind	35
2	Deaf	35
3	Slow learner	6
4	Down Syndrome	2
5	Mentally disabled	3
6	Autism	1
7	Mental disorder	1
8	Physical impairment	13
Total amount		96

Source: Center for Disabilities Services, 2023

In addition, there are also three lecturers with disabilities, two are blind, and the other one has physical impairment. The results of the observation and interviews are as follows:

1. Physical Access

Concerning the library's physical access, there 3 areas to note: the outside area of the library, the entrance to the library, and the access to the library services and collections. The Library of Sunan Kalijaga State Islamic University has a big enough parking lot for bikes, motorcycles, and cars, but it lacks for space signed with international symbols for the disabled. This shows that the library has not specifically provided a parking lot for the users with disabilities. The distance from the parking lot to the front door of the library is 6 meters, and the library users have to cross a rather busy area, which is not quite save for the disabled, before they get into the library. The area around the front door, however, is free and can be used as a parking lot for the disabled. In the meantime, it is easy to get to the front door as the access to it is spacy, with no barrier around and a very good lighting system. The library building is also completed with ramps, which are not steep and are not slippery (as they are made from cement), and are good for wheelchairs. The stairs are not steep either, and are completed with hand holdings on both sides.

Fig. 1. Outside Library

The result of the observation on the outside area of the library can be summarized as follows:

Table 3

Observation Results on the Outside Area of the Library

ELEMENT	STANDARD	Availability
Outside area of the library	1. Sufficient parking spaces marked with the international symbol for the disabled	x
	2. Parking close to the library entrance	v
	3. Clear and easy-to-read signposting	v
	4. Unobstructed and well-lighted access paths to the entrance	v
	5. Smooth and non-slip surface at the entrance	v
	6. If needed, a non-slip and not-too-steep ramp with railings next to the stairs	v
	7. Railings at both sides of the ramp	x
	8. Entry phone accessible for deaf users	x

Getting into the library

The path to get into the library is basically accessible for all users with wheelchairs. The library does not have an automatic front door. However, its front door (consisting of two pieces of door) is designed in such a way that it can open widely, reaching as wide as 180 cm. During service time, this front door is always open, and so are the other doors to get into the rooms of the library, so that the users with wheelchairs can easily get in. There is even a space (3 meters wide) in front of the front door that allows a wheelchair to turn around. This situation is also good for users with low vision (blind users). They are safe to get into the library, with no worry of crushing a glass door, even though there is no sign on it. There is no doorstep around the front door, which is good for blind users and users with wheelchairs.

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There is no security checkpoint at this front door, and all users can get in unquestioned. Security checkpoint is done only for those entering second–fourth floors for collection, circulation, and reference services. There is no elevator in this library building, and the users with disabilities, primarily users with wheelchairs, can only access the library services on the first floor. On this floor, they are specifically served in a special room called *Difabel Corner*. The second floor – fourth floors are not accessible for most disabled users, still, they are made good and accessible for users with low vision. The tips of the stairs are painted bright color, which is in contrast to the color of the stairs, this way the users with low vision will risk less (stay safe, being able not to slip). It is interesting to note that even though disabled users cannot access the second floor to the fourth floor due to the lack of elevator, they still can access the books available upstairs by OPAC and the librarians will bring the books they want to the *difabel corner*. Users with disabilities can read the book at *difabel corner* or do the borrowing process on the first floor.

The front door of the library

stairs

Fig. 2. Getting into library

The result of the observation on the access to the library for disabled users, referring to the IFLA Checklist, can be seen below:

Table 4

Observation Results on the Access to the Library for Users with Disabilities

Element	Standard	Availability
Getting into the library	1. Sufficient space in front of the door to allow a wheelchair to turn around	v
	2. Entrance door wide enough to allow a wheelchair to enter	v
	3. Automatic door opener reachable by a person in a wheelchair	x
	4. No doorsteps - for easy wheelchair access	v
	5. Glass doors marked to warn visually impaired persons	x
	6. Security checkpoints possible to pass through with a wheelchair/walker or other mobility aides	v

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7. Stairs and steps marked with a contrasting color	v
8. Pictogram signs leading to elevators	x
9. Well lighted elevators with buttons and signs in Braille and synthetic speech	x
10. Elevator buttons reachable from a wheelchair	x

Access to materials and services

The Library of Sunan Kalijaga State Islamic University has tried to make its services and collections, particularly printed collections placed on the shelves, easy to access. The bookshelves are about 200 cm high and consist of four levels. To take the books to the fourth level, users with wheelchairs will need help from the librarians. The spaces between shelves are wide enough so that users with wheelchairs can comfortably reach or access the books. There is no barrier in these spaces so users with wheelchairs can move with ease.

Another facility the library should provide is toilets comfortable for users with disabilities. In this library, the path to the available toilets has been completed with a pictogram, however small, as a sign for users with disabilities. In addition, there is a symbol for deaf users, and a braille alphabet attached to the door of the toilet to help the deaf users and the blind users choose the toilet they need. This library provides a toilet special for users with wheelchairs, with a door as wide as 120 cm, which allows a user with a standard-sized wheelchair to get in easily and safely. The room of this special toilet is also wide, that is, 160 cm wide and 200 cm long. It is completed with a washbasin of 80 cm in height, which is good for users with wheelchairs. There is also a mirror attached rather high on the wall, still a user with a wheelchair can use it to see his/her face.

Because the library applies a self-service borrowing system on the third floor, and the building is not completed with either an elevator or a ramp, blind users and users with wheelchairs cannot manage to access its circulation service. In this case, they need help from the available volunteers or the library staff. Book returning service, however, is done on the first floor, and disabled users can access it by themselves. Another service, which is inaccessible for users with disabilities, is the reference service because it is provided on the second floor. Even though, the reference service room, with good-sized reference tables in it, which are accessible for users with wheelchairs, is good enough for disabled users. Another thing to note is that the reference service chairs are not too high, completed with strong hand holdings safe for disabled users. Faced with this situation, the library came up with an idea of how its reference service stays accessible for disabled users, that is, by providing WhatsApp reference consultation, using first-chat first-reply system, in which all chats are replied to sequentially on the same day.

One of the library services that is the most helpful for users with disabilities is the existence of a department for the users with reading, hearing, and other disabilities, that is, *Difabel Corner*, located in a strategic, reachable place (close to the front door of the library) in the first floor. There is also a tactile line in the form of yellow guiding block to lead, in particular, the blind users and users with low vision. What is more of this guiding block is that it stretches toward many rooms, leading the blind users and users with low vision not only to the *Difabel Corner* but also to the other important rooms, like the administration room, toilet, and the other service rooms in the first floor. The *Difabel Corner*, with a signpost on its door, is usually used by the users with disabilities both for accessing the library collection and for gathering, and that is why the room is completed with a table, some chairs and sofas. The chairs do not have sturdy armrests, but the height of the table is good for the users with wheelchairs.

To support the library collections accesses, the *Difabel Corner* is completed with Aby Find Reader/OCR and a computer with screen reader software (Job Access with Speech/JAWS) for

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reading, scanning, and converting printed collections to audible ones. In addition, the Corner also provides a digital collection reading tool, that is, a digital talking book player, a computer with screen reader software (JAWS), a Digital Talking Book (DTB) player, and also a Closed-Circuit Television (CCTV) to bald printed writing to be readable for the users with low vision.

Space between bookshelves and a wheelchair

Sign language and braille: Toilet door

Difabel Corner Room

Fig. 3. Access to collections and services

The result of the observation on the accesses to the services and collections for the users with disabilities, with reference to the IFLA Checklist:

Table 5

Observation Result on Access to Services and Collections for Users with Disabilities

Element	Standard	Availability
1. The physical space	Clear and easy-to-read signs with pictograms	v
	Shelves reachable from a wheelchair	v
	Reading and computer tables of varying heights throughout the library	v
	Chairs with sturdy armrests	v
	Unobstructed aisles between bookcases	v
	Visible and audible fire alarm	x
	Staff trained to assist patrons in case of emergency	x
2. Toilets	Clear signs with pictogram indicating the location of the toilets	v
	Door wide enough for a wheelchair to enter and sufficient space for a wheelchair to turn around	v
	Room enough for a wheelchair to pull up next to the toilet seat	v
	Alarm button is reachable for persons in wheelchairs	x
	Washbasin, mirror at the appropriate height	v
3. Circulation desk	Adjustable desk	x

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	Induction loop system for hearing-impaired persons	x
	Chairs for elderly and disabled customers	x
	Accessible self-service circulation stations	v
4. Reference/ information desk	Adjustable desk	x
	Organized “queue system” in the waiting area	x
	Chairs suitable for elderly and disabled patrons	x
	Induction loop system for hearing-impaired persons	x
5. Department for persons with reading, hearing, and other disabilities	A centrally located department with talking books and other materials for persons with reading disabilities	v
	A coloured (yellow for visibility) tactile line leads to this special department	v
	Clear signs	v
	Comfortable seating area with bright reading light	v
	A tape recorder, CD player, DAISY (Digital Audio Information System) player 1) and other equipment to complement the audiovisual collection	v
	Magnifying glass, illuminated magnifier, electronic reader or closed-circuit television (CCTV)	v
	Computers with screen adapters and software designed for persons with reading and cognitive disabilities	v

2. Media Format

Library collections are an important element in performing library services, but when it comes to users with disabilities, the collections must be available in a special format. For blind users, the Library of Sunan Kalijaga State Islamic University provides collections in the form of digital talking books accessible online at <https://difarepositories.uin-suka.ac.id/>. For blind users, this library provides as many as 229 book titles in various subjects, like political science, law science, philosophy, religion, history, education, etc. In order not to break the copyright, these collections can only be accessed by blind users by logging with a username and a password given by the admin. In addition to these online collections, the library also provides Braille collections, which are 63 exemplars of Al Quran and several books in other subjects.

In addition to the collections accessible for users with disabilities, the *Difable Corner* provides a computer with screen reader software (JAWS) that is very helpful for blind users to access electronic collections. The computer is also supported with an adaptive keyboard, which produces sounds helpful for blind users to type.

Table 6

Observation Results on Media Formats Provided by the Library

Element	Standard	Availability
1. Special media formats for persons with disabilities	Talking books, talking newspapers, and talking periodicals	v
	Large print books	x
	Easy-to-read books	x
	Braille books	v

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	Video/DVD books with subtitles and/or sign language	x
	E-books	v
	Tactile picture books	x
2. Computers	Designated computer workstations adapted for patrons in wheelchairs	v
	Adaptive keyboards or keyboard overlays for users with motor impairments	v
	Designated computers equipped with screen reading programs, enlargement, and synthetic speech	v
	Designated computers equipped with spelling, and other instructional software suitable for persons with dyslexia	x
	Technical support for computers (on-site, if possible)	x
	Staff capable of instructing customers in the use of computers	v

3. Service and communication

Friendly library services for people with disabilities should be supported by library staff. This is the reason why the Library of Sunan Kalijaga State Islamic University appoints one of its librarians to be responsible for the *Difabel Corner* and act as a liaison person with disabled groups. This librarian is good at communicating with users with disabilities, particularly with blind users and physically disabled users. However, this librarian still finds difficulties in communicating the deaf users. Other than that, this librarian needs to be more knowledgeable about various types of disabilities because the students of this university consist mostly of deaf and physically disabled persons. Therefore, the library needs more volunteers who normally come from the Center for Disabilities. Although the library does not provide specific services, like outreach programs, it helps users with disabilities by providing needed facilities, like scanning tools to make texts accessible on a computer with the screen reader available in the *Difabel Corner*. In addition, the library offers guided library tours (called “Difa Tours”) for users with visual impairment. These are held at a certain time, like when the library celebrates the Library Visit Day. In these activities, blind users are taught how to access the library collections.

The library also regularly updates information concerning the library activities through the social media Instagram. These information updates are made in such a way that are also accessible for users with disabilities. They are presented in the form of clear, short texts, and infographics. They can be accessed by users with disabilities, even by deaf users as they are audible. The same is true with the library website. It can easily be accessed by users with disabilities. The website can be accessed easily because it separates the content (HTML) from the design (CSS). The library uses HTML to present OPAC, digital collections, service information, and news. Style sheets/CSS are used to control the visual page appearance, including the layout, color, and text style. All these have helped the users find and use the library resources. This can be seen from the library homepage or the website of Sunan Kalijaga State Islamic University. Here CSS is used to design the appearance of the header, footer, navigation, main content, space column, element position, and room division to make an easy-to-navigate homepage or website with a structured appearance. The style and color selection very often follow the color pallet and brand guidance of the institution. The Library of Sunan Kalijag State Islamic University uses white and green colors because they are the color symbol of Sunan Kalijaga State Islamic University.

The last aspect of service and communication standards is the aspect of cooperation. The Library of Sunan Kalijaga State Islamic University has limited human resources and this has pushed it to make cooperation work with other institutions. Since the founding of *Difabel Corner*, the library has (and still does) cooperation with the Center for Disabilities Service Center either in the procurement of facilities and collections or in volunteer recruitment.

In addition, based on the interview with the librarians, the library has also cooperation with some other institutions, among others, with AKADINI to hold an event of sharing and motivating parents to be always there for their blind children, and to involve the AKADINI human resources for *Living Collection Program* on parenting a disabled child theme. The library also made cooperated with *Braillean Community* to hold a meditation activity for blind students. Another activity involving other communities was conducted by UIN Sunan Kalijaga Library incorporated with the Association of Indonesian People with Disabilities aiming at educating people with disabilities with financial literacy. These cooperations with other institutions dealing with issues of people with disabilities shows that UIN Sunan Kalijaga Library is actively involved in promoting disability issues in the academic environment.

In addition, the library also makes a promotion for disability by making posters on disabilities, like sign language posters, and attaching them to each door of the library.

Table 7

Observation Results on Service and Communication

ELEMENT	STANDARD	Availability
1. How to train staff	1. A designated employee should act as a liaison person with disability groups and support organizations	v
	2. Staff be knowledgeable about various types of disabilities and how to assist the patron best	x
	3. Staff should also communicate directly with the patron and not through a caregiver	x
2. Special services to patrons with disabilities	1. Home delivery service to persons who are not able to come to the library	x
	2. Outreach services to persons in institutions and care facilities	x
	3. Reading service for patrons with reading difficulties (e.g., short texts, letters, instructions, articles on tape or CD) or scanning texts to make them accessible on a computer with the screen reader	v
	4. Regularly scheduled consultations for persons with reading disabilities	x
3. How to provide information to patrons with disabilities	1. The library should offer guided tours of the library for both individuals and groups of persons with special needs	v
	2. Provide a list of resources for all types of disabilities	x
4. How do you make information easy to understand?	1. Write clear and concise short sentences	v
	2. Avoid foreign words	v
	3. Insert ample white space between paragraphs and text blocks	v

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	4. Include illustrations on same page as accompanying text	v
	5. Use dark text on white or light coloured background – never light text on a dark background	v
5. Website	1. Make the design logical and easy to navigate	v
	2. Provide software to enlarge text, change font and contrast, length of lines, and space between lines	v
	3. Give alternative formats to .pdf and .doc -- preferably unformatted text (.txt)	v
	4. Separate contents from design – use style sheets to guide presentation and layout	v
	5. Include search capability on your website	v
	6. Avoid frames and tables, moving figures and texts	v
	7. Use relative measurements for text	v
	8. Accompany audio with text	v
6. How to cooperate with disability organizations and individuals	Cooperation with representatives of disability organizations and individuals is important in order to reach all citizens and establish credibility for the library's services and programs	v

The gap between the Checklist and the Condition of the Library of Sunan Kalijaga State Islamic University

In the study of Library and Information Science, disability is closely related to the social models that think that people with disabilities are not disabled because they are impaired. They are disabled because of the barriers created by society ignorant of the needs of all members of society (Ferrara, 2024). People with disabilities are also considered independent living models, experts in their experiences, who can decide what service they need and how to use it (Pionke, 2016). It is society, therefore, that can create a supportive condition for the disabled groups to be equal to the non-disabled group, by eliminating the barriers the disabled group finds in accessing the needed services. The Library of Sunan Kalijaga State Islamic University has endeavored to become a place accessible to users with disabilities. Referring to the IFLA Checklist, we see that the library has fulfilled most of the criteria for providing library services for people with disabilities. Still, there is one aspect that the library lacks and that is the physical aspect. The library building is not equipped with an elevator, which is very important for the disabled users to access the library services provided on the upper floors. The fact that there are 13 users with physical impairment should be the reason for the library to equip its building with an elevator. The existence of *Difabel Corner*, however, has been a big help so far. Other than that, the 35 deaf users should also be provided with some other facilities, like video collections with subtitles. Apart from this condition, the library collections as a whole, particularly the printed ones and e-journal, are good because deaf users can basically access them. Moreover, there are helpful companions (volunteers) from *Difabel Service Center* to accompany the deaf users. Another problem to solve is the fact that the

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library staff need to improve their ability to communicate with deaf users for a better understanding of their needs. The ability to communicate with disabled users is very important because it makes them feel more accepted and as a result they will have a good perception of the library, which is very important for the development of the library (Al, Dogan, Soydal, & Taskin, 2019). Concerning the library's human resources, the library has appointed one person (librarian) to act as a liaison person to the disabled users, but his/her main duty is on the information field, not to manage specifically the *Difabel Corner*. The daily operation of the *Difabel Corner* is handled by a volunteer, who is a blind student.

A gap also occurs in the reference service aspect. According to the IFLA Checklist, a reference service is not completely fulfilled without the availability of adjustment desks, a queue system, and chairs for the elderly. But, thanks to the development of technology, reference services for disabled users are performed through social media, like WhatsApp and Instagram. There are also some minor lacks of facilities, like large print collections and talking book collections for children, but they do not really matter for disabled users. The Library of Sunan Kalijaga State Islamic University is an academic library performing services for the academic society, and collections for children are not part of the must-be-available collections in this library. In addition, although the library does not have a large print collection, it provides reading facilities for visually impaired and blind users, i.e., electronic collections that can be read using a computer with assistive technology. The last thing the library lacks is an automatic door opener. As explained earlier, the front door of the library is always open during service time and any user can easily get in. In a tropical country, it is no problem to have the door always opened, and an open door may contribute to air circulation. Therefore, the unavailability of an automatic door opener does not hinder users, including disabled users, from getting into the library.

Conclusion

Under its inclusive parent institution, the Library of Sunan Kalijaga State Islamic University has an obligation to provide accessible collections and services for all users, including users with disabilities. For its users with various disabilities, the library has provided the needed facilities and services. It has fulfilled some of the service standards made by IFLA, particularly those concerning services for the users with visual impairment and the users with physical impairment. Still, there are two things the library needs to improve. First, the library does not have an elevator, which is important to support the services performed on the upper floors, like collection services, circulation services, and reference services. The existence of *Difabel Corner* has indeed been a big help for users with disabilities, but in the long run and for maximum benefit, an elevator is needed. Secondly, the librarian who manages the *Difabel Corner* is not well-trained and handles the information aspect only. So, the library needs a well-trained librarian (to have enough knowledge about various sorts of disabilities and be skillful in dealing with disabled users) with specific tasks to manage the department for persons with reading, hearing, and other disabilities (the *Difabel Corner*.) so that the library gives maximum benefits to the disabled users.

Implications for research, practice and/or society. Based on the gaps that occurred, this research can be used as a baseline for recommendations for UIN Sunan Kalijaga to further improve the accessibility of services for users with disabilities by completing facilities and programs that do not meet the needs of people with disabilities. It also can be used to develop policies to improve service for all, either people with disabilities or non-disabilities. The results of the research can also be a model for other libraries, especially university libraries to develop disability-friendly libraries.

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Доступність бібліотеки Державного ісламського університету ім. Сунана Каліджаги для студентів з обмеженими можливостями: оцінка

Мета. Це дослідження має на меті визначити доступність бібліотеки Державного ісламського університету ім. Сунана Каліджаги для користувачів з інвалідністю, щоб виявити розрив між стандартом бібліотечного обслуговування людей з інвалідністю та станом бібліотеки для підтримки доступного середовища. **Методика.** У цьому дослідженні застосовано якісні методи для вивчення доступності бібліотечних послуг для користувачів з інвалідністю за допомогою контрольного списку ІФЛА – стандарту надання бібліотечних послуг для людей з інвалідністю, що складається з 3 основних напрямків: фізичного доступу, медіаформату, обслуговування та комунікації. **Результати.** Бібліотека Державного ісламського університету ім. Сунана Каліджаги відповідає більшості критеріїв для надання послуг користувачам з інвалідністю. Фізичний доступ, що охоплює територію за межами бібліотеки, вхід до бібліотеки та доступ до бібліотечних фондів і послуг значною мірою відповідають стандарту. Однак відсутність ліфта не дозволяє користувачам на інвалідних візках піднятися на верхній поверх, де зберігаються бібліотечні фонди, а це означає, що доступ до бібліотечних фондів є ускладненим. Для вирішення цієї проблеми в бібліотеці створено «Куточок обмежених можливостей» – відділ для користувачів з усіма видами інвалідності. Дослідження також виявило, що для незрячих бібліотека надає більший доступ до бібліотечних фондів, тоді як для глухих він все ще не є максимальним. Тому бібліотека у співпраці з Центром обслуговування осіб з інвалідністю надає послуги волонтерів студентам, для яких вимоги інклюзії ще не виконані. **Висновки.** Перебування у підпорядкуванні головної установи, яка просуває інклюзивні цінності, вимагає від бібліотеки Державного ісламського університету ім. Сунана Каліджаги забезпечити інклюзивне середовище, яке вітає всіх користувачів незалежно від їхніх здібностей. Бібліотека доклала певних зусиль, щоб відповідати стандартам бібліотеки для людей з обмеженими можливостями. Розрив між ідеальними стандартами і реальними умовами в бібліотеці щодо доступності для людей з обмеженими можливостями може бути врахований для покращення інклюзивних бібліотечних послуг.

Ключові слова: бібліотечне обслуговування; люди з інвалідністю; академічна бібліотека

Received: 30.08.2024

Accepted: 03.12.2024